

A Snake in the Glass: Wet tank setup and focus stack imaging method for reptile and amphibian specimens

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Fluid-preserved reptile and amphibian specimens are challenging to photograph due to their complex three dimensional forms and reflective surfaces when removed from solution. A wet tank setup combined with focus stack photography is a useful approach to counteract these issues and generate high-quality images for publication and remote examination of fine traits. Imaging specimens beneath a layer of preservative fluid reduces risk of desiccation and glare, while focus stacking merges multiple images taken at different focal depths to create a single composite image with a broad depth of field, ensuring all anatomy is in focus even under zoom magnification. This presentation will provide an overview of wet imaging station components and the focus stack photography workflow implemented by the University of Colorado Museum of Natural History Herpetology Collection for the NSF-funded oMeso digitization project (NSF #2001474 Digitization PEN: Opening Mesoamerican Herpetofaunal Diversity to Whole Phenome Imaging).

